

Codebook – Lay theories of peace

* Variables used in this study

* associations of peace:

- * a_justice -> justice
- * a_endwar -> end war
- * a_harmonay -> harmony
- * a_endbs -> end bloodshed
- * a_partner -> partnership
- * a_equal -> equality

* interpretations of peace

- * negative peace -> negative
- * positive peace -> positive
- * structural peace -> struc2

* lay theories of peace

- * preferring positive over negative interpretations (PoN) -> posiovernega
- * preferring structural over negative interpretations (SoN) -> struc2overnega
- * preferring structural over positive interpretations (SoP) -> struc2overpositive

* Wish for conflict resolution strategy

- * wish for the One-State solution -> wishes_1
- * wish for the Two-State solution -> wishes_2

* Covariates used in this study

* nationality -> NAT

* NAT==1 -> Jewish Israeli sample

* NAT==0 -> Palestinian sample

* political ideology -> EOC (high score indicate hawkish ideology) constructed from 5 items

* The [ingroup] have an exclusive claim to the land of [ingroup] as it has been their homeland for generations -> eoc_1

* [ingroup] have always aspired for peace -> eoc_2

* [ingroup] have always been subjected to disproportionate aggression from the side of the [outgroup] -> eoc_4

* I do not believe in the peaceful intentions of the [outgroup] -> eoc_5

* In times of threat for the [ingroup], it is important to take armed action, even if it means harming civilians from the opposing side -> eoc_6

* gender -> gen

* gen = 0 -> male

* gen = 1 -> female

* education -> edu (highest diploma)

* edu = 1 -> less than highschool

* edu = 2 -> highschool

* edu = 3 -> BA

* edu = 4 -> MA and up

* religion -> relig

* relig = 1 -> not religious

* relig = 2 -> somewhat religious

* relig = 3 -> religious

* relig = 4 -> very religious

* age -> age

* Surveying method -> metho

* metho = 0 -> self filled survey

* metho = 1 -> face to face interview

* Other measures used in the Hope Map Project

- * political efficacy 1 -> effi_1
- * political efficacy 2 -> effi_2
- * acceptance of uncertainty 1 -> UNC
- * acceptance of uncertainty 2 -> unce_2
- * frequency of thinking about peace 1-> frq_1
- * frequency of thinking about peace 2-> frq_2
- * wish for generic reciprocal peace 1-> wishp
- * wish for generic reciprocal peace 2-> wishc
- * wish for generic reciprocal peace 3-> wishg_3
- * wish for generic reciprocal peace 4-> wishg_4
- * expectations for generic reciprocal peace 1-> expep
- * expectations for generic reciprocal peace 2-> expec
- * expectations for generic reciprocal peace 3-> expeg_3
- * expectations for generic reciprocal peace 4-> expeg_4
- * expectations for the 1SS -> expes_1
- * expectations for the 2SS -> expes_2
- * meta perceptions wish for generic reciprocal peace 1 of the Other - metaw_1
- * meta perceptions wish for generic reciprocal peace 2 of the Other - metaw_2
- * meta perceptions expectations for generic reciprocal peace 1 of the Other - metae_1
- * meta perceptions expectations for generic reciprocal peace 2 of the Other - metae_2
- * willingness to act for peace 1 -> act_1
- * willingness to act for peace 2 -> act_2
- * willingness to act for peace 3 -> act_3
- * referendum 1 -> refer_1
- * referendum 2 -> refer_2
- * perceived likelihood of threat 1 -> threatl
- * perceived likelihood of threat 2 -> threl_2

- * perceived severity of threat 1 -> threai
- * perceived likelihood of threat 2 -> threi_2
- * region (west bank/gaza) -> region
- * district in Israel and the OPT -> dist
- * resident of city/village/refugee camp (only Palestinians) -> resi
- * party affiliation Israel and the OPT -> politica

* Codes used in the study:

*constructing interpretations of peace (peace types) (see S8 in SI)

* negative peace

alpha a_endwar a_endbs gen positive

* positive peace

alpha a_harmony a_partner gen positive

*structural peace

alpha a_justice a_equal gen struc2

* exploratory factor analysis showing how associations of peace load on interpretations (see S9 in SI)

factor a_endwar a_endbs a_harmony a_partner a_equal a_justice, ipf

rotate, promax

* confirmatory FA was done for each sample using janovi software - see repository

* percentage of Israelis who strongly or very strongly associate peace with:

*Negative peace

tab negative if negative >= 4 & NAT==1

*Positive peace

tab positive if positive >= 4 & NAT==1

*structural peace

tab struc2 if struc2 >= 4 & NAT==1

* percentage of Palestinians who strongly or very strongly associate peace with:

* Negative peace

tab negative if negative >= 4 & NAT==0

* Positive peace

tab positive if positive >= 4 & NAT==0

* Structural peace

tab struc2 if struc2 >= 4 & NAT==0

* Comparing interpretations of peace between samples

* Negative peace

ttest negative, by (NAT)

* Positive peace

ttest positive, by (NAT)

* Structural peace

ttest struc2, by (NAT)

*Comparing interpretations of peace within subjects (Table S1 in SI)

* negative peace vs positive peace

ttest negative=positive

ttest negative=positive if NAT==0

ttest negative=positive if NAT==1

* negative peace vs structural peace

ttest negative=struc2

ttest negative=struc2 if NAT==0

ttest negative=struc2 if NAT==1

* positive peace vs structural peace

ttest positive=struc2

ttest positive=struc2 if NAT==0

ttest positive=struc2 if NAT==1

* Correlations between interpretations

pwcorr negative positive struc2, sig

* constructing "lay theories of peace" variables

* PoN

gen posiovernega = positive - negative

* SoN

gen struc2overnega = struc2 - negative

* SoP

gen struc2overpositive = struc2 - positive

* comparing lay theories of peace to zero

* PoN

ttest posiovernega=0

* SoN

ttest struc2overnega=0

* SoP

ttest struc2overpositive=0

* predicting lay theories of peace

* PoN

```
reg posiovernega NAT EOC age gen relig edu metho
```

```
margins , at (NAT=0 NAT=1)
```

```
estat esize
```

* SoN

```
reg struc2overnega NAT EOC age gen relig edu metho
```

```
margins , at (NAT=0 NAT=1)
```

```
estat esize
```

* SoP

```
reg struc2overpositive NAT EOC age gen relig edu metho
```

```
margins , at (NAT=0 NAT=1)
```

```
estat esize
```

* Comparing the wish for sharing (1SS) vs. dividing (2SS) between samples (S6 in SI)

* wish for 1SS

```
ttest wishes_1, by (NAT)
```

* wish for 2SS

```
ttest wishes_2, by (NAT)
```

* Comparing the wish for sharing (1SS) vs. dividing (2SS) within subjects (S6 in SI)

* entire sample

```
ttest wishes_1=wishes_2
```

* Palestinian sample

```
ttest wishes_1=wishes_2 if NAT==0
```

* Israeli sample

```
ttest wishes_1=wishes_2 if NAT==1
```

* predicting the wish for sharing resources (1SS) by lay theories of peace

*Positive over negative interpretations

```
reg wishes_1 c.posiovernega###NAT struc2 EOC age gen relig edu metho
estat esize
```

*Structural over negative interpretations

```
reg wishes_1 c.struc2overnega###NAT positive EOC age gen relig edu metho
estat esize
```

*Structural over positive interpretations

```
reg wishes_1 c.struc2overpositive###NAT negative EOC age gen relig edu metho
estat esize
```

* predicting the wish for dividing resources (2SS) by lay theories of peace

*Positive over negative interpretations

```
reg wishes_2 c.posiovernega###NAT struc2 EOC age gen relig edu metho
estat esize
```

*Structural over negative interpretations

```
reg wishes_2 c.struc2overnega###NAT positive EOC age gen relig edu metho
estat esize
```

*Structural over positive interpretations

```
reg wishes_2 c.struc2overpositive###NAT negative EOC age gen relig edu metho
estat esize
```

* constructing the measure for political ideology (EOC)

```
alpha eoc_1 eoc_2 eoc_4 eoc_5 eoc_6 gen EOC
```

* questions? Please contact Dr. Oded Adomi Leshem oleshem@gmu.edu